

“BIODIVERSITY, FOOD AND EDUCATION. A PLAN FOR FUTURE ACTIONS”

Results from the Symposium of the 25 November 2024

Università degli Studi di Milano-Bicocca

NBFC

“The tree of life” Artwork by Marwan Abdulmajeed

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Contents:

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	1
	1
ACTIONS	2
1. Publications	2
2. Education	2
3. Art and exhibitions	3
4. Cooperation (international)	3
5. Networking/ Advocacy/Lobbying	4
Tools	4
Strategic suggestions (for all actions):	4
CHALLENGES, LIMITS, CRITICAL POINT	6
1. Knowledge and awareness	6
2. Educational strategies	7
3. Widening and spreading	7
4. Governance aspects	8
5. Planning aspects	9
6. Loss of points of reference	11
CRITICAL ISSUES AND THEIR RELATION TO THE PROPOSED ACTIONS	12
ANNEXES	14
ANNEX 1 - METHODOLOGY	15
ANNEX 2 - POSITION PAPER	18
Context	18
Biodiversity, Food Systems and Culture	19
The role of museums, ecomuseums and other cultural institutions	20
The topics of the symposium and open questions	21
ANNEX 3 - PARTICIPANTS	24

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In the following line, we will summarise the results of the symposium, while more details can be found in the following section.

- The discussion developed at the tables allowed to integrate the experiences and point of view of both academic and practitioners who, with different approaches, work on the topics of biodiversity, food systems sustainability, education and museology.
- The discussion highlighted the need to improve the knowledge and awareness on these three topics and on their relations, challenging old views. The critical issues concerning this macro-aim relate,
 - on one hand to the ability to reach and activate different populations and stakeholders, promoting networks from the local to the global level;
 - on the other to the strategic planning that should characterize this effort, regarding financial support, styles of governance, assessment methodologies and so on.

A number of actions and **tools** was suggested, according to the highlighted needs and aims:

- Different kinds of **Publications**, including:
 - a special issue on the relation between biodiversity, food systems and education;
 - a policy brief directed at politicians and administrators.
- **Education and exhibition** including:
 - the realization of a kit for temporary exhibitions;
 - the promotion of a master on biodiversity, food and sustainability;
 - the promotion of various forms of collaborations between artists, museums and representatives of the food system and rural communities.
- **Cooperations**, including the definition of research agreements between universities and the mapping of food systems.
- Action of **networking/advocacy/lobbying**, starting with the follow up of the work and the connections stemming from the symposium.

ACTIONS

1. PUBLICATIONS

1.1 Special issue on international, open access journal (ie: Sustainability) (end December 2025).

1.2 Policy brief/ White Paper. Include agreements with ecomuseums and local institutions working on biodiversity topics. A joint document or White Paper should be created and shared with ministries.

Timetable: from January 2025 to December 2025

2. EDUCATION

2.1 Master. Develop guidelines for a Master on Museums Biodiversity, Food and Sustainability.

Timetable: end March 2025

2.2 KIT for temporary exhibitions.

In partnership with ICOM Italia - International Council of Museums. Develop a ready to use stand alone KIT for temporary exhibitions on biodiversity, to be used by different museums and adaptable (to their collections and specific needs) and implementable. First possible locations: Vivaio Bicocca or Museo Bicocca. Verifying other locations. The kit could include plans for **citizen science** projects.

Practical exhibitions on ecosystems, food chains and sustainable agriculture, based on up-to-date scientific data. The exhibitions could also include panels to be displayed outdoors along the gates of the Milan Museum of Natural History and the Aquarium (Parco Montanelli and Sempione).

Timetable: Work in progress. Design ends March 2025. Construction ends May 2025

Webinar. "Museums, Ecomuseums & Biodiversity - with a focus on food and communities"
Possible date 22th May 2025 for the International Day of Biodiversity. Identify participants and partners for the activity (end of January).

Practical activities for the public on cultivation, composting and sustainable techniques, developed with the support of researchers and academics. These activities could take place on a rotating basis in green areas, ie: in Milano, as well as in the Museum of Natural History and the Aquarium, they could involve the Green sector of the Municipality of Milan.

Timetable: 22th May 2024

2.3 Annual conferences. Participating - thanks to the Symposium Network - in annual conferences organized by the Association linked to museums, ecomuseums and cultural

institutions, but not only, involving different stakeholders. Such as FAO (Live Seeding) and others.

2.4 AI experiences:

Use the AI to create interactive modules and enhance learning experiences related to biodiversity and food systems.

Use of digital tools such as virtual reality and simulations, developed in collaboration with research institutes, to show the human impact on ecosystems. Digital tools could also be implemented as part of widespread projects in the city (ie: the project 'The museum under the house' implemented by the Natural History Museum).

2.5 Internships. Promote collaborations between universities and museum to support the involvement of youth in internship experiences that will provide economic support and encourage the youth to stay in rural areas.

2.6 Training for museum staff. Organize learning and training for the staff on participatory and experiential approaches with a focus on interaction with youth (in particular, age between 18 and 25).

3. ART AND EXHIBITIONS

3.1. Guidelines.

Develop Guidelines for temporary and permanent exhibitions to highlight: a need for the balance of power between museum, the artist and people, through action of co-design, collaboration, participation. The artists should follow a non extractive art projects approach. Artists should help to overcome the link human- non human and the wholeness with nature.

Guidelines for ecological transition in museums highlighting small activities (e.g. [CIMAM Guidelines - Toolkit on Sustainability in the Museum Practice](#))

3.2 Residency. reinterpretation of collections, collaboration between different stakeholders (e.g farmers) and artists and public events showcasing the interaction between artists and farmers.

3.3 Opening museums: Museums could offer spaces for free for community's activities, act as connection between the administration and the communities, support new and "temporary" communities, including Erasmus students, stagiast and so on.

4. COOPERATION (INTERNATIONAL)

4.1 'Mediterranean Diplomacy'. Continue the activities for the 'Mediterranean Diplomacy' (Algeria, Morocco, and Tanzania) and implement relations with other museums and ecomuseums in the African Mediterranean area and beyond.

- The need for closer collaboration with communication experts was highlighted, to enhance the impact of any action promoted.
- Accessible and engaging narratives based on academic studies to raise public awareness of global challenges: narratives could invade the city through a communication plan involving posters, also produced in collaboration with artists and using augmented reality.
- Ecomuseums must apply the principle of horizontal subsidiarity: horizontal collaboration between public and private interest: where it is missing, they can take the place of the bar, neighbourhood shop, political dialogue, church, according to the philosophy of *Oikos* (home, common good).
- Ecomuseums have to aim at self-sufficiency, through cooperation at a local territorial level, where they hold more credibility.
- Continues communication, dialogue, activities between the participants of the Symposium, to continue the work and make it happen, even online.
- Universities should focus their actions to maximise their impact as instrument of contrast of cultural homologation and neofascist tendencies.

CHALLENGES, LIMITS, CRITICAL POINT

1. KNOWLEDGE AND AWARENESS

1. There is a deficit of knowledge on ecology and biodiversity: the entanglements between biodiversity, climate change, and health are neither clearly understood nor adequately promoted.
2. Need to refine and clarify terminologies, particularly focusing on defining "biodiversity" to ensure a shared understanding and effective communication
3. Need to focus on real-world challenges for museums and ecomuseums, in particular climate change and biodiversity. There are already examples of best practices (ie: Jordan Museum).
4. Key topics included
 - a. the concepts of living heritage,
 - b. citizen science, and the use of tools like the Naturalist App;
 - c. seed biodiversity;
 - d. the role that the promotion of local food products can have on local ecosystems.
5. Tourists are a population that needs to be educated, for example via the topic of local food.

Challenge (aesthetic) standards

1. Need to change the aesthetic approach that leads to unsustainable practices (i.e. gardens with tall grass require too much chemical products and fertilizers).
2. Lack of guidelines for the management of external areas for museum and ecomuseums with sustainable criteria.
3. Need to encourage diversity, local traditions, and health.

Challenge divide human/nature

1. Restore identity: It's not something external, we are nature.
2. Restore food identity and revise food policies. A lot of talks and valorisation around food, but little narrative around the link between food and health. Political strategies should prioritize and valorise high-quality food. E.g. in areas like Naples, which faces high rates of obesity. What do youth think nature is? E.g. Marseille – Mediterranean diet. 3 main issues are highlighted: 1. the cost of the food supply chain, linked with a low spending capacity; 2. humans do not perceive themselves as nature; 3. promoting different kind of food production such as permaculture, regenerative agriculture and others. (this last activity is something that museums can do).

2. EDUCATIONAL STRATEGIES

1. The traditional teaching paradigm (frontal class) is not enough.
2. Culture and biodiversity need to be addressed simultaneously, building knowledge, demonstrating practical alternatives, and fostering active engagement.
3. Need to differentiate activities according to different populations and level of competence.
4. Need to create new narratives and storytelling approaches to effectively communicate these ideas.
5. Need to rethink the museum experience:
 - a. to better represent the new reality of agriculture
 - b. in light, also of climate change and biodiversity crisis
6. Importance of an experiential dimension was emphasized, focusing on grounding efforts in local traditions and practical, hands-on experiences to strengthen connections with biodiversity and food systems.
7. Technology museums were highlighted as key players, with the potential use of AI to create explainers and enhance learning experiences related to biodiversity and food systems.

3. WIDENING AND SPREADING

Involvement of Youth

1. It is challenging for museums and ecomuseums to engage with different generations. Strategies need to be developed to bridge this gap.
2. Youth is often “obliged” to pseudo-voluntary work, it is difficult to ask them to do more. They face economic issues.
3. In the last 20 years it has become more difficult to relate you youth as a “group”, there is a lack of cohesive institutions
4. Need to move from intergenerational conflict to proactive dialog between generations
5. There is a lack of digital communication, that is more effective with youth
6. Involving the young generation - especially the target between 18-25 or the young active for the climate - requires the involvement since the very beginning of projects and in the decision, they prefer to be partners of the project. Some museums require institutional/administrative agreements to proceed with co-design and collaboration.
7. Food systems can be a door in:
 - a. in Italy there are many UK and USA students interested in the food culture;
 - b. in the U.S., children often lack exposure to natural foods, which impacts their biological and sensory experiences. In contrast, primary school children tend to be very active and sensitive, demonstrating a deeper understanding of such critical themes. In New Zealand, young people are notably motivated by the urgency of the climate emergency.

Involvement of older people

1. Need to commit the older generation to change (we have always done things in another way, why should we change...).
2. Need to overcome a certain intergenerational conflict and go to fruitful collaboration.
3. Need to dialogue with the past was also encouraged to deepen understanding and inspire future actions.

Cross-cluster interventions

1. There is a gap between clusters and different cultural ecosystems.
2. To fill the gap, there is need for cross-sector actions
 - a. museums and academic/research worlds;
 - b. whoever projects an intervention and the real need of the local community. Sometime the research developed by universities can fill this gap.

International collaboration

1. Need for more exchanges between countries to share best practices, not only cultural exchanges.
2. In Italy, some excellence exists but lacks the ability to integrate into a wider, international network, overcoming the local dimension and creating new connections.
3. Rethinking the spatial scale of action, advocating for work at the bio-regional and transnational levels. The importance of circular processes, both traditional and historical, was highlighted, along with the use of available funds, such as INTERREG.
4. Need to foster a strong network across ecomuseums in Europe, using tools like a geoportal for building connections. The difficulty of ensuring sustainability in such networks was acknowledged.

4. GOVERNANCE ASPECTS

Top-down vs bottom-up

1. Top down and bottom-up approaches need to be used in the right way.
2. The governance must integrate both approaches.
3. The governance needs to be more participative.
4. Value of local knowledge was highlighted, urging its inclusion in higher governance levels, local rootedness and engagement. It was noted that legislation can sometimes be an obstacle, particularly with standards in public procurement and the management of key landscapes.

Active participation

1. Need to activating participation: the engagement of people requires a constant effort, cannot be achieved with spot interventions.
2. Often the community doesn't seem to feel the need to participate. But once the process is activated, there is appreciation for it.
3. The promotion of processes of community empowerment is a precise task of all administrative levels, defined by European policies, only rarely carried out effectively.

Involvement all stakeholders

1. Involvement of all communities - different stakeholders such as public and private sector, companies, politicians, and in general the public and different interest-based communities - is essential:
 - a. to gain a vision of the real needs of the population and the territory;
 - b. to find an administrative solution that can root in the territory.
2. In the food system, this means involving not only consumers and museum visitors but also key stakeholders across the food chain, including producers, retailers, and policymakers.
3. Need for actionable steps, not just educational initiatives.
4. Need to calibrate interventions depending on the territorial scale we are working with:
 - a. need to be able to work with single persons;
 - b. but also, with associations and other collective entities.
5. Need to develop intersectionality.
6. Linking actions across similar environments to encourage replication and foster collaboration among communities.
7. Need for multilevel partnerships involving universities, ecomuseums, local associations, and other institutions, with a focus on maintaining engagement and benefiting from the network.
8. Importance of an innovation ecosystem was emphasized, involving ongoing collaboration between institutions like UNIMIB, PolMi, Polito, UniPavia, Pollenzo, and Brescia.

5. PLANNING ASPECTS

Impact assessment

1. Impact assessment is fundamental to evaluate intervention and support their continuity and funding.
2. There is a need for tools, indexes, long term impact measures, most of all there is a measure concerning results (outputs and not outcome).

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- a. e.g. in UK measurement of the impact of electrical buses after ten years of their introduction.
 - b. Nowadays, in Italy many funding calls by bank Foundations (such as Fondazione Compagnia di San Paolo, Fondazione Cariplo) outcomes and KPIs are required before and after the project. PERSEA. Eurostat Index.
 - c. Some tools quoted: Habenet; - MOI; - Itaca Fair (it works very well with the population, especially with young people)– for tourism and food; the [inside-outside model](#) of Douglas Worth and Raul del Santo (2022).

Access to data

1. Lack of or difficult access to data: Finding the data necessary to do research is often difficult. To overcome this problem, we try to weave relationships on the ground, talking to different actors to understand how practices influence the processes of food narratives that take shape on the ground.
2. Lack of human resources to be able to study a territory.

Communication/greenwashing

1. Communication is now more mainstream and less biodiversity friendly.
2. Need to avoid greenwashing.
3. Need to explain better how climate change affects health.
4. Lack of communication skills impact:
 - a. ability to share the knowledge built through projects, that risk to remain only known among experts;
 - b. ability of small realities to find a place in bigger, international networks.

Affordable solutions

1. With food (as an example) sustainable options are often expensive:
 - a. consumer doesn't really understand why, and the benefit of choosing that option (e.g for health);
 - b. the economic support that government address to the agricultural sector rarely have a positive impact on the consumer.
2. Need to incorporate innovative practices that are viable, also economically.

Long terms commitments

1. When starting an action, attention should be put to its maintenance for long term - often is too much or too little.
2. Long term commitment is linked to Governance aspects and Strategic Planning, to impact especially at local level in small Municipalities.
3. There is a lack of National strategic vision, at least in Italy, that impacts:

- a. the funding opportunities.
- b. the promotion of cultural awareness

One participant observe that “Italy is a fresco whose beauty is enhanced by single brushstrokes and single colours in a system that tends to globalise everything”. No overall strategies are identified and there is a dispersion of local identities, experiences and resources.

4. Once a network is created, it's often challenging to maintain it alive after the first round of financing has ended.
5. Cultural awareness is a way to long term commitment.

Economic aspects

1. Structural deficit: resources are given as isolated initiatives, depending on very rigid public finances.
2. Economic deficit: there is a constant lack of resources, and a general disorganisation a lack of system.
3. Lack of economic resources to attract young people.
4. Proactive engagement was emphasised, connecting to current funding opportunities and creating functional networks.

6. LOSS OF POINTS OF REFERENCE

1. Loss of reference points by the people of the territory, which is constantly changing.
2. Loss of credibility and significance of institutions and administrations. The ecomuseums protect a place, make it desirable, even in an area considered disadvantaged.
3. Whoever comes from outside proposes a project, collaboration with the community, and once that project is over, leaves. The ecomuseum should protect from this “extractive” approach.
4. Institutional crises in internal areas have become topics of extra-institutional political debate, producing some of the most interesting ideas from the perspective of community and togetherness, though all at an informal level. There is difficulty in formalizing this debate within established museum networks, as opposed to institutional ones, creating a need to develop the ability to build informal, thematic networks that are distinct in nature.

CRITICAL ISSUES AND THEIR RELATION TO THE PROPOSED ACTIONS

Although we recognize the overall interconnectedness of the issue highlighted, and the multiple impacts that the actions proposed would have on them, we tried to connect each group of action to the main critical issues that could be affected by them.

ANNEX 1 - METHODOLOGY

The Symposium "Biodiversity, food and education. What role for museums, eco-museums and other cultural institutions," organized by the University of Milano-Bicocca and the National Biodiversity Future Center, Spoke 7 (nbfc.it), was held on November 25, 2024, at the University of Milano-Bicocca from 9:30 a.m. to 5:00 p.m.

The goal of the Symposium was not only to start a conversation, but also to propose actions that will help make progress in bridging the gap between theory and practice, especially in the fields of biodiversity conservation and food system sustainability

This symposium is one of the results of the National Biodiversity Future Centre (NBFC), a project funded by the Ministry of University and Research (MUR) through European Union funds. The Center was established in Italy and is a coordinating structure, organized in Spokes and involving more than 2,000 stakeholders.

Spoke 7 aims to communicate, enhance and share with the international audience and Italian society, the contents emerging from the other thematic Spokes of the NBFC. The Spoke focuses on creating effective operational interfaces to connect the world of biodiversity research with policy makers, ministries and all relevant public and private institutions and stakeholders.

In general, the actions of SPOKE 7 are driven by a belief that is also the starting point of this symposium: there can be no ecological transition without a societal commitment to genuine ecology. In order to stimulate this societal commitment, it is important to define a set of actions / practices that significantly contribute to build a discourse, or a way of thinking aimed at raising awareness among people about the value of biodiversity conservation and promoting the sustainability of the food system.

To this aim, the theme of the symposium concerns how cultural institutions in general—and specifically museums and ecomuseums—, can help to reduce the gap between theory and practice in the fields of biodiversity conservation and food system sustainability through educational projects. The focus on practices and evaluation processes helps explore this central issue.

This is why we decided to organize three discussion tables that address all three questions, asking participants to contribute to the overall theme by offering reflections on either: Actions they have direct or indirect experience with, or/ and Evaluation strategies that have been implemented.

Participants. About thirty experts from various sectors and entities (associations, universities, ecomuseums, museums, private entities, and more) were identified, all working on the topics in question.

Position Paper. All participants were provided with a Position Paper, which focused on the context, the relationship between biodiversity and the cultural sector (museums and ecomuseums, but not limited to them), with an emphasis on sustainability in the food system

and biodiversity conservation. The document addressed relevant issues and what museums and other cultural institutions can do to raise awareness among different categories of subjects on related topics.

Symposium Purpose. The aim of the Symposium was to reflect on what museums and other cultural institutions can do to raise public awareness and promote participatory practices on the themes of biodiversity conservation and food system sustainability. The goal was to produce a shared document proposing actions aimed at overcoming the critical issues that emerged from the discussion.

Symposium. Brief presentations (in the morning). The day began with four short presentations introducing experiences in biodiversity, sustainable food systems, and environmental justice, with the following figures:

- Karen Brown, Professor at the University of St Andrews (Scotland), expert in Museums and Sustainability and President of ICOM-ICOFOM - focus on museums, food and biodiversity
- Hellas Cena, Professor at the University of Pavia, expert in Nutrition Science and coordinator of Spoke 6 of NBFC
- Pamela Koch, Professor at Columbia University, New York, expert in Nutrition and Education - focus on schools and food
- Tania Schusler, Professor at Loyola University of Chicago, expert in Social and Environmental Justice - focus on youth and environmental (biodiversity and food) and social equity/inequalities.

Symposium Discussion Tables. Next, moments of dialogue among participants were organized, structured in three parallel tables, followed by a final session for defining a shared document.

The discussion was organized in two subsequent moments.

In the first moment, the focus was on the current **state of the art** to identify critical points, limitations, and challenges, starting from questions aimed at investigating, for example, how museums and ecomuseums can contribute to reducing the **gap between theoretical knowledge and the practices** of the communities they are part of. What is the potential of community engagement activities that these institutions can develop in biodiversity conservation and promoting the sustainability of food systems? What can be done to involve different age groups and maximize the impact on young people? Another objective was to **address the systematization of experiences**, or what can be done to relate different experiences to facilitate the production of more coherent and organic knowledge. Another theme addressed concerned the **evaluation of impacts** and, for assessing the initiatives promoted, which elements are most frequently identified as positive or conducive to achieving goals. and what unites successful experiences, and what are the most frequently encountered obstacles.

In the second moment, **proposals for actions** were presented to overcome the criticalities and limits highlighted. Proposals included, for example, the possibility of creating: a series of strategic publications - also for policy development -, guidelines and a special edition of a scientific journal on the topic in question; educational and training supports, such as a

webinar, participation in conferences, the design of a Master's program dedicated to Biodiversity, Food, and Sustainability, an exhibition kit (intended as a ready-to-use standalone kit for temporary exhibitions on biodiversity, to be used by different museums and adaptable); international cooperation activities such as “Mediterranean Diplomacy” or inter-institutional collaborative and participatory moments. A series of tools were identified to support these actions.

Symposium. Presentation of results. In the last part of the day, the coordinators of the three roundtables presented the results, concerning both the criticalities and potentials that emerged and the **actions**. The goal is to produce a Document that synthesizes the results of the three roundtables and starts the phase of actions that can involve the different participants of the Symposium in 2025, based on the activities. Indeed, it emerged as a shared interest not to disperse the network and to continue the dialogue and open collaboration for implementing the various actions.

ANNEX 2 - POSITION PAPER

CONTEXT

The biodiversity crisis that we have caused, and we continue to face in the 21st century, is a fact and does not seem to be slowing down.

“We are living in an era of unprecedented environmental changes, in which climate change, habitat alteration, pollution, invasive species, and overexploitation all contribute to the decline of species” (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment 2005, IPBES 2019).

We cannot expect to reverse this trend solely through scientific research — although this is essential for understanding and classifying species and their interrelationships, as well as for comprehending the mechanisms of interaction with human activities — nor through environmental advocacy, which is necessary to raise collective awareness but can go unheard. The knowledge that is built through research and advocacy must become a resource for society as a whole through widespread shared initiatives.

The causes of the current biodiversity crisis are systemic (degradation of terrestrial and aquatic forests, invasive species, demographic growth and urbanization, soil and aquatic habitat destruction, pollution, indiscriminate exploitation of biological resources, climate warming, and extreme weather events) and therefore require systemic interventions.

We need paradigm shifts: new ways of living and consuming, new awareness, new limits and regulations, and behaviors that follow ecologically sound principles based on science. There can be no “ecological transition” without a societal commitment to genuine ecology, that is, without a strong strategic focus on biodiversity for its intrinsic value, ecosystems services that support our survival, and source of resilience for ecosystems and economic recovery. To work on these issues, the National Biodiversity Future Center (NBFC), funded by the Ministry of University and Research (MUR) through European Union funds – NextGenerationEU, was established in Italy. NBFC is a coordinating structure, involving more than 2,000 stakeholders, enhancing research efforts while simultaneously making knowledge and technologies accessible to various actors operating in the field. Within the NBFC, there is a specific area— Spoke 7—dedicated to Biodiversity and Society: Communication, Education, and Social Impact. The main objectives of this spoke include maximizing cross-sectoral relationships within different areas of society and fostering the dissemination of knowledge through the promotion of new languages and methods of science and biodiversity education and communication.

The Symposium has been organized within this context.

BIODIVERSITY, FOOD SYSTEMS AND CULTURE

Since the 1990s, awareness regarding the role of culture as a fourth pillar of sustainability has grown. An example of this recognition is the development of the “Agenda 21 for Culture” in 2003, complementing the United Nations' Agenda 21 established in Rio de Janeiro in 1992. In recent years, this concept has gained increasing traction in the cultural sector. To achieve the paradigm shift necessary to effectively address the ongoing environmental crisis, it is essential to foster a cultural transformation that involves not only scholars, scientists, and policymakers, but also society at large. In this context, culture is understood as “a system of inherited values, expressed in symbolic forms, through which humans communicate, perpetuate, and develop their knowledge and attitudes toward life” (Geertz, 1992). Thus, culture is viewed as a set of ways of thinking and acting that influence human behavior and can either steer individuals toward or away from sustainability. The question then becomes: what conditions are necessary for people to develop a sustainable “habitus” (Bourdieu, 1992) that enables them to protect and enhance their environment?

Specifically, this Symposium focuses on the connections between biodiversity, food production, and culture. It explores the multiple impacts that interventions within the intersections of these three domains can have. Industrial, monoculture, input-intensive food production is among the primary drivers of biodiversity loss. In turn, biodiversity loss affects nutritional food quality and, consequently, human health. Therefore, there is a need for actions that engage with communities on possible ways to mitigate harm to both people and the environment. At the same time, biodiversity represents the foundation of resilient ecosystems, essential for sustainable food production. Preserving biodiversity requires coordinated efforts to protect habitats, reduce negative human impacts, and promote practices favorable to ecological recovery. This involves not only conserving iconic species but also safeguarding the genetic diversity of flora and fauna, thus ensuring ecosystem resilience in the face of environmental disruptions (Mace et al., 2012). Developing food production systems that draw on cultural traditions can have positive outcomes for both food security and environmental sustainability. By preserving native seeds, promoting organic and regenerative farming methods, and valuing traditional knowledge, communities can not only protect biodiversity but also ensure food security for future generations. In this case, food production can strengthen communities, support local economies, and foster a deeper connection to the land (Altieri & Nicholls, 2020).

Efforts to conserve biodiversity and ensure equity within food systems entail building a system of values—upon which narratives and practices are based—that conveys widely accessible knowledge through diverse languages, capable of reaching various target populations. Education broadly conceived—not only as formal schooling but also as experiences that actively engage communities—is essential, as it leads to capacity-building. Education should thus be understood as an ensemble of experiences that develop knowledge, skills, and competencies for more effective community participation that enables communities to autonomously identify their needs, collectively engage in decision-making, and adopt measures toward a sustainable food system. Youth can play a particularly significant role in this area, though the effort must necessarily involve the entire population.

In building these experiences, cultural institutions of various kinds—particularly museums and eco-museums—play important roles. These institutions have already demonstrated considerable attention and sensitivity to these topics, especially through projects focused on community engagement.

THE ROLE OF MUSEUMS, ECOMUSEUMS AND OTHER CULTURAL INSTITUTIONS

One of the specific activities of Spoke 7 aims to deepen the involvement and role of museums and ecomuseums on biodiversity issues. They provide communities with information and represent shared cultural, educational, and training paths, capable of generating value. Museums and ecomuseums can engage with communities to promote the knowledge of nature, the languages of biodiversity, and the sharing of strategies for the protection and enhancement of natural resources, all of which are essential to support the ecological transition.

Museums and ecomuseums indeed play—or have the potential to play—a crucial role in supporting research, education, governance, and policies related to biodiversity and sustainable food systems. They can activate strategic networks and develop projects with local stakeholders and communities. Natural history and science museums were the first to engage in this area due to their collections, along with ecomuseums, which often have strong ties to their surrounding communities. These institutions have already launched several initiatives, collaborating with local communities and scientific research institutions. However, this potential is not limited to these types of museums; other museums can also promote biodiversity-related initiatives, even though their connections to biodiversity may not yet be as well-developed within the broader museum and cultural sectors.

In line with their new definition by the International Council of Museums (ICOM, 2022), museums are increasingly focused on sustainability. With an integrated approach, they can play a vital role in biodiversity conservation by initiating actions, disseminating scientific information, and raising awareness within both local and global communities. Current best practices include the use of museum collections for scientific research, engagement in scientific and citizen science projects, and social roles through awareness-raising, education, and public participation initiatives. Museums also contribute by managing green spaces and collaborating in urban nature projects or regenerative agriculture efforts.

THE TOPICS OF THE SYMPOSIUM AND OPEN QUESTIONS

The aim of the meeting is to discuss what museums and other cultural institutions can do to raise public awareness and promote participatory practices on the issues of biodiversity conservation and the sustainability of the food system.

The day will begin with four short speeches that will introduce experiences in the field of biodiversity, sustainable food systems and community engagement. It will continue with the organization of three tables that will operate in parallel discussions and convene in the last working session to develop a shared document.

Reflecting on the participatory experiences developed in projects aimed at the conservation of biodiversity and the promotion of sustainable food systems, the discussion will be organized around the following questions:

1) Bridging theory and practice

We know that through educational and participatory actions, museums stimulate processes of social, cultural and environmental change (Hauenschild, 2022). Recent studies suggest that the governance practices of local systems, for example food systems (Manganelli 2022, Halliday 2022), or initiatives aimed at biodiversity conservation (Visseren-Hamakers and Kok, 2022), can benefit from hybridization processes, which integrate non-conventional stakeholders. Museums, although not directly involved in food policies, can contribute to food co-governance practices to the extent that they use learning and capacity building tools that involve the local community or national and international visitors (Borrelli et al., in pub.).

How can cultural institutions, such as museums and ecomuseums, contribute to reducing the gap between theoretically developed knowledge and the practices of the communities in which they are embedded? What is the level of community engagement that these institutions can develop in conserving biodiversity and promoting the sustainability of food systems? What can we do to involve different age groups and maximise the impact on young people?

2) Cross-institutional learning and exchange of experiences

In the national and international panorama, several institutions are addressing the issues related to the conservation and restoration of biodiversity and those related to the sustainability of food systems. The ways in which they deal with these issues are very different, starting from artistic productions or exhibitions on the theme, such as the Field Museum of Chicago with the exhibition “Restoring Earth” or the Museum of the City of New York with the exhibition “Food in New York Bigger Than the Plate”. More and more often, cultural institutions (museums and ecomuseums) are starting to build networks with different local and supra-local stakeholders. Some examples of thematic networks are the Network of

Ecomusei del Gusto, in Piedmont Region, or the Museo del Cibo (Food Museums) in the Province of Parma. Collaboration in new networks and partnerships with different stakeholders and institutions emerges as fundamental to addressing current challenges. In many cases, these are inter-institutional networks between museums, local authorities, schools, communities and research and scientific institutions. This synergy becomes essential both for the conservation and restoration of biodiversity and for raising awareness among a wider public. Mobilizing institutions and individuals is essential for the success of the initiatives. These networks allow the sharing of resources, knowledge and experiences, promoting the development of sustainable practices. The commitment of museum associations also during annual national conferences and in their training and dissemination proposals, is pivotal to the dissemination of best practices among professionals in the cultural sector.

How can museums and ecomuseums share experiences across institutions and diverse community contexts? Which actions can be implemented to increase the diffusion of initiatives and to connect the different experiences/practices in order to facilitate a more coherent and organic production of knowledge?

3) Impact assessment

Impact evaluation and assessment of initiatives developed under different frameworks is an object of attention not only for researchers, but also politicians and activists. For example, within the Sustainable Development Goals framework, both conceptual aspects (such as the choice of indicators and the transition from theoretical definitions to measurable elements) and practical ones (such as how to fund data collection and analysis, who should be responsible for its execution) are the subject of debate. Issues also arise such as who has the appropriate training to conduct these evaluations, or how to organize training of new evaluators. These are common issues for all initiatives that aim to promote change and have an impact on local communities, as well as on a broader scale. In projects designed to promote change in a specific natural or social context, for example, evaluation is essential to understand the impacts of project activities. However, such impacts are often visible only in the long term, and their measurement can exceed the duration of the project, posing serious challenges to the validation of the results.

In evaluating the initiatives carried out, which elements are most frequently identified as positive or preparatory to achieving the objectives? What do successful experiences have in common, and what are the most frequently encountered obstacles?

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